

Rhenium chemistry of pyridyldiazoles : oxorhenium(V) and imidorhenium(V) species

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Abstract : The first diazole complexes of rhenium have been isolated and characterized in the form of the oxo and imido species of general type $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{L})]$ and $[\text{Re}(\text{NPh})\text{Cl}_3(\text{L})]$ where L is 2,5-bis(2-pyridyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole or 2,5-bis(2-pyridyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole. Structure determination has revealed meridional geometry, oxo/imido triple bonding and aromatic lattice interactions. The chelates display a relatively weak ligand field band in the visible region and a quasireversible $\text{Re}^{\text{VI}}/\text{Re}^{\text{V}}$ cyclic voltammetric response.

Keywords : Oxorhenium(V), imidorhenium(V), pyridyldiazoles, cyclic voltammetry.

Formation of oxo moieties constitute a dominant feature in the chemistry of the higher oxidation states of rhenium¹. In this laboratory we have been interested in the design and reactivity of new oxorhenium(V) reagents based on *N,N*-chelation by conjugated nitrogen-donor ligands². A notable reaction of oxorhenium(V) species is oxygen atom transfer to oxophilic substrates³⁻¹⁰.

The nitrogenous ligands employed so far generally have a pyridyl moiety, the second nitrogen site being either of acyclic – such as imine and azo – or of heterocyclic type². Our recent investigations have centered around the second alternative which has potentially wide scope encompassing the many variations possible in the form of the azaaromatic ligands. So far only pyridyldiazoles^{7,8} and certain bipyridine-like ligands⁹ have been scrutinized.

In the present work the case of two pyridyldiazole ligands is investigated. We describe the successful synthesis of their oxorhenium(V) complexes which are found to react with aromatic primary amines furnishing imido complexes. The spectral and electrochemical characterization of both types are described along with the structures of two representative members.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

The two diazole ligands concerning us in this work

are 2,5-bis(2-pyridyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (pyod, **1**) and 2,5-bis(2-pyridyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (pytd, **2**) and these were synthesized using available methods^{11,12}. The binding of these ligands to bivalent cobalt, nickel, copper and platinum have been reported¹³⁻¹⁷. To our knowledge nothing is known about the rhenium chemistry of pyod and pytd.

1, E = O, pyod

2, E = S, pytd

3, E = O, $[\text{Re}^{\text{V}}\text{OCl}_3(\text{pyod})]$

4, E = S, $[\text{Re}^{\text{V}}\text{OCl}_3(\text{pytd})]$

The equimolecular reaction of pyod with $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ in stirred benzene solution at room temperature afforded the orange-yellow oxo complex $[\text{Re}^{\text{V}}\text{OCl}_3(\text{pyod})]$, **3**, in excellent yield. The orange coloured thiadiazole complex $[\text{Re}^{\text{V}}\text{OCl}_3(\text{pytd})]$, **4**, was similarly prepared. The synthetic reaction is stated in eq. (1),

The oxo oxygen atom in **3** (**4** behaves similarly) is readily

substituted by the imido function upon reacting with aniline (PhNH₂) in solution. The transformation which

is essentially of acid-base type is stated in eq. (2). The blue coloured imido species [Re^V(NPh)Cl₃(pyod)], **5**, and [Re^V(NPh)Cl₃(pytd)], **6**, were isolated in excellent yields.

5, E = O. [Re^V(NPh)Cl₃(pyod)]

6, E = S. [Re^V(NPh)Cl₃(pytd)]

Structure and geometry :

The two pytd complexes **4** and **6** afforded suitable single crystals and their structures have been determined. Crystal data are listed in Table 1 and selected bond parameters are collected in Tables 2 and 3. Perspective molecular views are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The imido complex crystallizes as a dichloromethane adduct, **6**. CH₂Cl₂ in which the dichloromethane molecule does not display any noteworthy nonbonded contacts.

Table 1. Crystallographic data for [ReOCl₃(pytd)] and [Re(NPh)Cl₃(pytd)].CH₂Cl₂

	[ReOCl ₃ (pytd)]	[Re(NPh)Cl ₃ (pytd)].CH ₂ Cl ₂
Empirical formula	C ₁₂ H ₈ Cl ₃ N ₄ OSRe	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ Cl ₃ N ₅ SRe
Formula weight	548.83	708.87
Crystal system	Triclinic	Triclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> -1	<i>P</i> -1
<i>a</i> , Å	8.134(4)	7.732(3)
<i>b</i> , Å	8.380(4)	12.212(4)
<i>c</i> , Å	13.195(4)	14.451(7)
α , deg	95.36(3)	110.52(3)
β , deg	98.90(3)	93.88(3)
γ , deg	113.73(3)	107.50(3)
<i>V</i> , Å ³	801.4(6)	1195.7(8)
<i>Z</i>	2	2
ρ_{calcd} , mg m ⁻³	2.274	1.969
μ , mm ⁻¹	8.215	5.745
<i>R</i> ₁	0.0754	0.0746
<i>wR</i> ₂	0.1438	0.1792

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (deg) for [ReOCl₃(pytd)]

Distances			
Re-O1	1.701(14)	Re-Cl1	2.320(6)
Re-N1	2.31(2)	Re-Cl2	2.374(6)
Re-N2	2.11(2)	Re-Cl3	2.362(6)
Angles			
O1-Re-N2	92.5(6)	O1-Re-N1	163.6(6)
N2-Re-N1	71.1(6)	O1-Re-Cl1	106.2(5)
N2-Re-Cl1	161.3(4)	Cl1-Re-N1	90.2(4)
O1-Re-Cl3	99.4(6)	Cl3-Re-N2	89.4(5)
N1-Re-Cl3	81.2(4)	N2-Re-Cl2	89.4(4)
O1-Re-Cl2	98.6(6)	Cl1-Re-Cl3	87.2(2)
N1-Re-Cl2	81.4(4)	Cl1-Re-Cl2	88.2(2)
Cl3-Re-Cl2	162.0(2)		

Table 3. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (deg) for [Re(NPh)Cl₃(pytd)].CH₂Cl₂

Distances			
Re-N5	1.70(2)	Re-Cl1	2.360(5)
Re-N1	2.26(2)	Re-Cl2	2.385(5)
Re-N2	2.080(12)	Re-Cl3	2.391(5)
Angles			
N5-Re-N2	96.7(6)	N5-Re-N1	169.0(6)
N2-Re-N1	73.0(6)	N5-Re-Cl1	100.9(5)
N2-Re-Cl1	162.2(4)	Cl1-Re-N1	89.6(4)
N5-Re-Cl3	100.4(4)	Cl2-Re-N2	94.0(4)
N1-Re-Cl3	83.1(4)	N2-Re-Cl3	87.1(4)
N5-Re-Cl2	94.9(4)	Cl1-Re-Cl3	87.0(2)
N1-Re-Cl2	82.3(4)	Cl1-Re-Cl2	87.3(2)
Cl3-Re-Cl2	164.4(2)		

Fig. 1. Molecular view of [ReOCl₃(pytd)].

Fig. 2. Molecular view of [Re(NPh)Cl₃(pytd)].

The pytd ligand chelates in the bidentate mode with only one of the two pyridyl groups coordinating. This mode occurs quite generally in the few reported structures of the diazole ligands^{13–17}. The coordination geometry in both cases is distorted octahedral and the chloride ligands are meridionally disposed.

In the five membered chelate ring the pyridyl nitrogen N1 and the diazole nitrogen N2 lie respectively *trans* and *cis* to the oxo oxygen atom O1 (in **4**) or to the imido nitrogen atom N5 (in **6**). The three chloride ligands along with the N2 atom define a virtually perfect equatorial plane from which the metal atom is displaced by 0.36 Å towards O1 in **4** and by 0.32 Å towards N5 in **6**. The chelate ring along with the diazole ring and the coordinated pyridine ring define an approximate plane (mean deviation, 0.04–0.07 Å). The pendant pyridine ring is roughly coplanar with it (dihedral angle 2.2° in **4** and 10.8° in **6**). This is believed to be dictated by the π - π stacking interactions in the lattice (*vide infra*).

Bond parameters and bonding :

In **4** the Re-O distance, 1.701(14) Å, lie within the range observed^{2,6–10,18–20} for the Re^{VO} species, 1.68 ± 0.03 Å. The minimum Re^{VO}(oxo)^{21,22} distance reported is ~1.60 Å which corresponds to idealized triple bonding where three lone pairs are formally donated from the oxide ligand to the metal. For comparison we note that the corresponding double and single bond distances are ~1.76 Å^{21a,23,24} and ~2.05 Å^{25,26} respectively. In summary the Re-O length in **4** corresponds approximately to triple bonding, but with significant double bond character. The Re-N1 bond is subject to the *trans* influence of the oxo oxygen atom and is thus longer than the Re-N2 bond by ~0.2 Å.

Similarly in **6** the *trans* influence of the imido nitrogen lengthens Re-N1 bond by ~0.2 Å compared to the Re-N2 bond. Here the Re-N5 length, 1.70(2) Å, corresponds to triple bonding (idealized distance 1.69 Å)²⁷. The corresponding double bond length is 1.84 Å²⁸. The Re-N5-C13 moiety is approximately linear, the angle at N5 being 171.7(12)°. In hexacoordinated Re^V-imido species the Re-N(imido) bond length has been found to span the range 1.67–1.74 Å and the Re-N-C angle to span the range 160–180°^{29,30}.

Some qualitative aspects of bonding in [ReOCl₃(pytd)] will be considered assuming the idealized geometry, **7** with Re=O defining the Z-axis. The filled p_z orbital of

the oxo oxygen atom is used for the σ -hybridisation and the filled p_x, p_y orbitals are used for π -bonding with metal d_{xz}, d_{yz} orbitals. The latter orbitals are destabilized and the two metal electrons (Re^V, $5d^2$) occupy the d_{xy} orbital in a paired configuration. A relatively weak absorption band observed near 750 nm in the oxo species (*vide infra*) is tentatively assigned to the $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$ transition. The filled d_{xy} orbital can interact with the empty diazole $\pi^*(C=N)$ orbital, the sense of electron donation being $Re \rightarrow \pi^*$. A synergistic π interaction of type $\pi^* \leftarrow Re \leftarrow O$ is thus possible, provided the diazole nitrogen and the oxo oxygen atoms lie *cis* to each other as in the observed structure. The case of **6** can be similarly treated. Here the imido nitrogen atom replaces the oxo oxygen atom in **7**.

Nonbonded lattice interactions :

The lattice of **4** has significant nonbonded interactions as can be seen in the Fig. 3. The Re(pytd) fragments align nearly parallel to each other creating pairwise π - π interactions between the pendant pyridyl ring and the diazole ring of two symmetry related molecules. The distance between the centroids of the two rings is 3.68 Å, there being an offset of 24.3°. These parameters clearly reflect the presence of relatively strong attractive π - π interaction between the two molecules^{31,32}. The stacked pairs are associated via Cl...S contacts of 3.527 Å into an infinite pattern.

Fig. 3. Stacking diagram of $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pytd})]$ showing relevant parameters.

The lattice of **6** displays similar π - π interactions but between the pendant pyridyl ring and the phenyl ring of the imido ligand of symmetry related molecules. Each ring is involved in two π - π interactions leading to infinite supramolecules consisting of stacks in which the pytd ligands are parallel placed and so are the NPh ligands, as depicted in Fig. 4. The interactions of lengths 3.917 Å and 4.011 Å (centroid ...centroid in both cases) are associated with offset angles of 25.9° and 32.8° respectively.

Fig. 4. Stacking diagram of $[\text{Re}(\text{NPh})\text{Cl}_3(\text{pytd})]$ showing relevant parameters

Spectra :

Spectral data are listed in the experimental section. In IR the oxo complexes **3** and **4** display an $\text{Re}=\text{O}$ stretch near 990 cm^{-1} , two $\text{Re}-\text{Cl}$ stretches near 330 and 360 cm^{-1} and two $\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretches near 1600 and 1580 cm^{-1} . In the imido species **5** and **6** two $\text{Re}-\text{Cl}$ stretches and two $\text{C}=\text{N}$ stretches occur near 320 , 340 and 1600 , 1590 cm^{-1} respectively. In the visible region **3** and **4** display a relatively weak absorption band near 750 nm consistent with a large contribution from the ligand field excitation $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}$, d_{yz} . The imido species **5** and **6** also exhibit a similar band but of slightly higher intensity near 740 nm .

The reported complexes are all diamagnetic (d_{xy}^2) and give rise to well-resolved ^1H NMR lines. In the free ligands the two pyridyl rings are magnetically equivalent

in solution. In the complexes the two pyridyl rings are evidently inequivalent (see Experimental section).

Metal redox :

Both the oxo and the imido species are electroactive in acetonitrile solution and display quasireversible (peak-to-peak separation 80–100 mV) one-electron couples due to $\text{Re}^{\text{VI}}/\text{Re}^{\text{V}}$ redox (eqs. (3) and (4)). Cyclic voltammetric data are collected in Table 4 and two

representative voltammograms are displayed in Fig. 5. The reduction potentials of the oxo complexes ($\sim 1.60\text{ V}$ versus SCE) are much higher than those of imido species ($\sim 0.90\text{ V}$ versus SCE) signifying superior stabilisation of Re^{VI} state upon imido coordination as compared to oxo coordination. The difference between the reduction potentials of corresponding pyod and pytd complexes is small.

Table 4. Cyclic voltammetric formal potentials for **3-6** in acetonitrile solution at 298 K

Compd.	$E_{1/2}$, V (ΔE_p , mV) $\text{Re}^{\text{VI}}/\text{Re}^{\text{V}}$
3, $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pyod})]$	1.64(80)
4, $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pytd})]$	1.62(90)
5, $[\text{Re}(\text{NPh})\text{Cl}_3(\text{pyod})]$	0.96(80)
6, $[\text{Re}(\text{NPh})\text{Cl}_3(\text{pytd})]$	0.95(80)

Fig. 5. Cyclic voltammogram of (a) $[\text{Re}^{\text{V}}\text{OCl}_3(\text{pytd})]$ and (b) $[\text{Re}^{\text{V}}(\text{NPh})\text{Cl}_3(\text{pytd})]$ in acetonitrile solution.

Clearly defined metal reduction (say from +5 to +4 or +3 states) could not be observed electrochemically. However, chemical reduction of the oxo complexes is readily achieved. Thus tertiary phosphines afford triva-

lent complexes such as $[\text{Re}^{\text{III}}(\text{OPPh}_3)\text{Cl}_3(\text{pyod})]$ (eq. (5)). The dynamics of this transformation as well as structure and properties of the trivalent complexes are under scrutiny and will be published elsewhere.

Conclusion :

Scrutiny of diazole chemistry of rhenium has been initiated via synthesis and characterization of the oxo complexes which have afforded imido complexes upon reaction with aniline.

Structure determination of $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pytd})]$ and $[\text{Re}(\text{NPh})\text{Cl}_3(\text{pytd})]$ has revealed meridional geometries in which the coordinating pyridine ring is disposed *trans* to the oxo/imido group. The bond order of both Re-O(oxo) and Re-N(imido) is approximately 3. Interesting modes of π - π stacking occurs in the lattices of both $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pytd})]$ and $[\text{Re}(\text{NPh})\text{Cl}_3(\text{pytd})]$.

The complexes are uniformly diamagnetic and a relatively weak band in the region 730–760 nm is believed to have considerable ligand field character. The quasireversible one-electron $\text{Re}^{\text{VI}}/\text{Re}^{\text{V}}$ reduction potential is much higher in the oxo (~ 1.6 V) than in the imido (~ 0.9 V) complexes signifying superior stabilization of the hexavalent state upon imido coordination.

Experimental

Materials :

2,5-Bis(2-pyridyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole¹¹, 2,5-bis(2-pyridyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole¹² and the $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ complex³³ were prepared by reported methods. The purification and drying of dichloromethane and acetonitrile for spectral and electrochemical work were done as before³⁴. Benzene was distilled over sodium before use. All other chemicals and solvents were of reagent grade and were used as received.

Physical measurements :

UV-vis spectral measurements were carried out with a Shimadzu UVPC 1601 spectrometer fitted with thermostated cell compartments. IR spectra (4000–100 cm^{-1}) were recorded in KBr disk with the help of Perkin-Elmer L-0100 and Nicolet Magna IR 750 Series II spectrometers. Proton NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker FT 300 MHz spectrometer. The atom numbering scheme used in ¹H NMR is the same as in crystallography. Spin-spin structures are abbreviated as follows : s, singlet; d, doublet; t, triplet; m, multiplet. Electrochemical mea-

surements were performed under nitrogen atmosphere on a CH 620A electrochemical analyzer, using a platinum working electrode. The supporting electrolyte was tetraethylammonium perchlorate (TEAP), and potentials are referred to the saturated calomel electrode (SCE). The symbols used for cyclic voltammetric potentials are as follows : E_{pa} , anodic peak potential in V; E_{pc} , cathodic peak potential in V; ΔE_p is the difference between E_{pa} and E_{pc} in mV; $E_{1/2}$, half wave potential (reduction potential) which is calculated as the average of E_{pa} and E_{pc} i.e. $E_{1/2} = 1/2 (E_{\text{pa}} + E_{\text{pc}})$. The solute concentration used for voltammetry is $\sim 10^{-3}$ M and the supporting electrolyte (Et_4NClO_4 , concentration : ~ 0.1 M). The scan rate is generally 50 mV s^{-1} . Microanalyses (C, H, N) were performed using a Perkin-Elmer 2400 series II elemental analyzer.

Synthesis of complexes :

The two oxo complexes were prepared by the same general procedure and details are given below for the pyod complex. To a suspension of $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ (100 mg, 0.12 mmol) in 50 ml of benzene was added 27 mg (0.12 mmol) of pyod. The resulting mass was stirred magnetically for 4 h at room temperature affording a turbid orange yellow solution which was kept undisturbed overnight to ensure complete precipitation. The orange yellow solid, $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pyod})]$, was collected by filtration, washed thoroughly with benzene, and finally dried in vacuum over fused CaCl_2 . Yield : 43 mg (67%). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{Cl}_3\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{Re}$: C, 27.05; H, 1.51; N, 10.52. Found : C, 27.12; H, 1.45; N, 10.45. UV-vis (λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$), CH_2Cl_2 solution) : 754(140), 469(2400), 310(12350). ¹H NMR δ in ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) 8.91 (1H, d, J 5.1 Hz), 8.70 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 8.65 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 8.57 (1H, t, J 7.6 Hz), 8.25 (1H, d, J 8.2 Hz), 8.11 (1H, t, J 8.4 Hz), 8.04 (1H, t, J 8.7 Hz), 7.73 (1H, t, J 6.5 Hz).

$[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pytd})]$. Yield 70%. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_8\text{Cl}_3\text{N}_4\text{OSRe}$: C, 26.26; H, 1.47; N, 10.21. Found : C, 26.16; H, 1.53; N, 10.14. UV-vis (λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$), CH_2Cl_2 solution) : 756(200), 493(2800), 315(15050). ¹H NMR δ in ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) 8.74 (1H, d, J 5.2 Hz), 8.54 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 8.49 (1H, d, J 6.9 Hz), 8.40 (1H, t, J 7.1 Hz), 8.09 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz), 7.91 (2H, t, J 8.8 Hz), 7.57 (1H, t, J 6.4 Hz).

The same general method was used for the synthesis of the two imido complexes and details are given below for $[\text{Re}(\text{NPh})\text{Cl}_3(\text{pytd})]$. To a solution of $[\text{ReOCl}_3(\text{pytd})]$ (64 mg, 0.12 mmol) in dichloromethane (15 ml) was added aniline (56 mg, 0.60 mmol) in benzene (50 ml) and the

mixture was heated to reflux for 2 h affording a blue solution. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the mass thus obtained was subjected to chromatography on a silica gel column (20 × 1 cm, 60–120 mesh). Excess aniline was eluted with benzene. A blue band was then eluted with a benzene-acetonitrile (25 : 1) mixture. Solvent removal from the eluate under reduced pressure afforded [Re(NPh)Cl₃(pytd)] as blue solid. Yield : 85 mg (81%). Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₃Cl₃N₅Re : C, 34.65; H, 2.10; N, 11.22. Found : C, 34.72; H, 2.04; N, 11.29. UV-vis (λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), CH₂Cl₂ solution) : 747(580), 586(1960), 444^s(520), 412^s(870), 321(10180). ¹H NMR δ in (CDCl₃) pytd, 9.51 (1H, d, *J* 5.7 Hz), 8.68 (1H, d, *J* 4.0 Hz), 8.04 (1H, t, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.82 (2H, m), 7.64 (1H, d, *J* 7.9 Hz), 7.53 (1H, t, *J* 5.8 Hz), 7.13 (1H, t, *J* 6.7 Hz); NPh, 7.97 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.88 (1H, t, *J* 7.5 Hz), 7.43 (2H, t, *J* 7.8 Hz).

[Re(NPh)Cl₃(pyod)]. Yield : 83%. Anal. Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₃Cl₃N₅ORe : C, 35.56; H, 2.16; N, 9.22. Found : C, 35.62; H, 2.21; N, 9.26. UV-vis (λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), CH₂Cl₂ solution) : 739(480), 582(1610), 440^s(430), 406^s(690), 319(7830). ¹H NMR δ in (CDCl₃) pyod, 9.51 (1H, d, *J* 5.9 Hz), 8.68 (1H, d, *J* 4.4 Hz), 8.04 (1H, t, *J* 7.7 Hz), 7.86 (2H, m), 7.79 (1H, d, *J* 7.1 Hz), 7.64 (1H, d, *J* 7.4 Hz), 7.54 (1H, t, *J* 5.7 Hz); NPh, 7.97 (2H, d, *J* 8.2 Hz), 7.43 (2H, t, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.13 (1H, t, *J* 6.7 Hz).

X-Ray structure determination :

Single crystals of the complexes [ReOCl₃(pytd)] and [Re(NPh)Cl₃(pytd)] were grown by slow diffusion of hexane in dichloromethane solutions of the respective compounds. Data were collected on a Nicolet R3m/V four circle diffractometer with graphite-monochromated Mo-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) by the ω -scan technique in the range $3^\circ \leq 2\theta < 50^\circ$. All data were corrected for Lorentz-polarization and absorption³⁵. The metal atoms were located from Patterson maps and the rest of the non-hydrogen atoms emerged from successive Fourier syntheses. The structures were then refined by full-matrix least-squares procedure on *F*². All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. All hydrogen atoms were included in calculated positions. Calculations were performed using the SHELXTLTM V 5.03 program package³⁶.

Crystallographic data for the complexes has been deposited to Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre : CCDC reference numbers are 601328 (for [ReOCl₃(pytd)]) and 601329 (for [Re(NPh)Cl₃(pytd)]). These data can be

obtained free of charge from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.

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